

Syntheses of 2-carboxy-2',4'-diamino azo benzene and 2-nitro-2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl azo benzene and their use as acid-base indicators

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Abstract : The present paper describes the studies on acid-base characteristics of two synthesized novel azo-dyes. The isosbestic points and apparent pK_{In} values of them have been determined spectrophotometrically. These dyes can be used as pH indicators for estimation of strength of the mixtures of acids, bases and salts. The parameters measuring the performance of indicators have been also evaluated with the help of UV-visible and IR-spectroscopy and conductivity measurements and comparison of our indicators have been also made with some known indicators like methyl orange and phenolphthalein. The study shows better performance of our synthesized indicators, particularly for titration of dilute solutions.

Keywords : Azo-dyes, pH indicators.

In continuation of our work on the synthesis of a novel azo-dye indicator namely 2-carboxy-2',4'-diamino azo benzene (I_1) and the characterization of it with reference to application in jute industry¹, hereby we are reporting synthesis and characterization of another novel azo-dye 2-nitro-2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl azo benzene (I_2). We are also reporting here the acid base behaviour of these two successive azo-dyes from spectrophotometric and conductometric studies.

Results and discussion

These two azo dyes have been synthesized by diazotization of anthranilic acid and *ortho*-nitro aniline followed by coupling with sodium acetate solution of *meta*-phenylene diamine and *meta*-cresol. This azo dye (I_1) has been characterized earlier¹. The elemental analysis data of compound (I_2) is as follows : {percentage found (calcd.)} C, 60.55 (60.95); H, 4.58 (4.46); N, 16.14 (16.34). The stretching frequencies of the bands are at 1525 (aromatic NO_2), 1608 ($-N=N-$), 2910 (phenolic $-OH$), 2962 cm^{-1} ($-CH_3$). The vibration frequencies are at 1608/1526 ($-N-H$), 2725 cm^{-1} (weaker $-OH$). Due to the presence of chromophoric groups like $-NO_2$, $-N=N-$, $-OR$ etc. in the compound I_2 , it can act as an excellent dye for various purposes.

Acid base properties of I_1 and I_2 :

The UV-visible spectra of the reagents I_1 and I_2 (Figs. 1a and 1b, respectively) for both of their acidic and basic

Fig. 1a. Spectra of acidic and basic forms of I_1 indicator.

forms show the existence of isosbestic points at wavelength $\lambda = 416$ and 390 nm respectively. This suggests that the two conjugate acid-base pairs are characterized by their maximum absorbances at 470 and 410 nm for the former and 365 and 465 nm for the latter. The determination of dissociation constant pK_{In} , for indicator I_1 , confirms the existence of equilibrium between the yellowish red form HIn in acidic medium and the greenish yellow In^- in alkaline medium, similar to acid-base phenomenon of methyl orange² (Fig. 2a). Accordingly pK_{In} for I_2 (Fig. 2b) assures the equilibrium between the green form, HIn , in acid medium and yellowish red neutral form In^- present

Fig. 1b. Spectra of acidic and basic forms of I_2 indicator.

Fig. 2a. Equilibrium characteristics of 2-carboxy-2',4'-diamino azo benzene (I_1).

Fig. 2b. Equilibrium characteristics of 2-nitro-2'-hydroxy-4'-methyl azo benzene (I_2).

in weakly alkaline medium. The experimental observations are in agreement with the results reported in IR and UV studies³. The pH transition range for change of colour of solution with indicator I_1 is 6.00–7.73 and indicator I_2 is 6.98–8.29. Thus pH transition range which is nearly 7

and pK_{In} values of the reagents (6.73 for I_1 and 7.78 for I_2 at 35 °C), indicate that these reagents are fit to act as indicators for titration of both strong and weak acid with strong alkali.

Molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) values of these two indicators were compared with those of a standard indicator like methyl orange (Table 1).

Fig. 1a reveals that absorption of the acid form decreases sharply with respect to its basic form beyond 410 nm, i.e. in the violet-UV region, resulting a deepening of two steps of observable complementary colour from green to red. The data presented in Table 1 also reveal that on addition of acid, molar extinction coefficient and hence absorption of I_1 increases about 2.5 times at $\lambda_{max} = 470$ nm, for the conversion In^- to HIn , although only a very small decrease of molar extinction coefficient takes place at 410 nm. Such change of colour from green to red for the conversion from In^- to HIn is also possible due to a significant absorption of the acid form of the indicator (Fig. 1a) in the range of 470–500 nm with respect to its basic form In^- . Moreover increase of absorption at 470 nm due to above mentioned conversion makes the solution more yellow coloured. Thus an overall deepening of colour occurs from greenish-yellow to yellowish-red for titration of an alkali with an acid in presence of indicator I_1 .

For indicator I_2 , as depicted in Fig. 1b, λ_{max} for the acid form appears in the near UV region viz. at 365 nm, indicating absorption of violet and UV rays and thus its visible complementary colour appears as green in the acid form where such absorption is greater. Moreover a significant absorption of the basic form of indicator I_2 at 465 nm and onwards up to 500 nm makes the complementary colour of I_2 yellowish-red. Thus a sharp color change from green to yellowish-red can be obtained for the titration of an acid with an alkali.

For comparison of the performance of the indicators we follow the essence of an earlier method for conductometric measurements⁴. For studying conductometric ti-

Table 1. Molar extinction coefficients ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) of I_1 , I_2 and methyl orange at the λ_{max} of their acidic and basic forms

Extreme medium	For I_1		For I_2		For methyl orange	
	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$ (at λ_{max} 470 nm)	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$ (at λ_{max} 410 nm)	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$ (at λ_{max} 365 nm)	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$ (at λ_{max} 465 nm)	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$ (at λ_{max} 480 nm)	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$ (at λ_{max} 515 nm)
In alkaline solution	0.008	0.010	0.222	0.638	0.203	0.092
In acidic solution	0.020	0.009	0.521	0.046	0.221	0.369

tration an aliquot of 20 ml 0.004 (*N*) HCl diluted by 80 ml triple-distilled water was taken. After addition of each indicator solution the mixture was titrated with 0.04 (*N*) NaOH solution added from a microburette. From a perusal of Fig. 3, it is evident that the color transition point with the indicator I_1 and I_2 are very near to the actual equivalence point found from conductometric titration.

Fig. 3. Conductometric titration of a dilute strong acid with a strong base in presence of I_1 , I_2 , I_3 (methyl orange) and I_4 (phenolphthalein).

Considering conductometric titration as a method for analyzing different indicator titrations, an error in the volume of titre requirement with respect to the volume required in the conductometric titration, arises as 5% for I_1 , while similar errors is 20% for methyl orange, 40% for I_2 and 65% for phenolphthalein (Fig. 3). This reveals that the order of performance among the indicators studied for titration between a strong acid and a strong base is as follows : $I_1 >$ methyl orange $>$ $I_2 >$ phenolphthalein.

Conclusion :

The two indicators I_1 and I_2 are obtained respectively by coupling anthranilic acid with *meta*-phenylene diamine and *ortho*-nitro aniline with *meta*-cresol. Indicators I_1 and I_2 (exist in aqueous solution) show different structural forms depending on pH. The variation of the absorbance with the wavelength for these two indicator solutions at different pH values has shown the existence of two stable forms. For I_1 , the colour of the one form is yellowish-red in acidic medium ($1.0 < \text{pH} < 6.0$) having $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 470$ nm and the color of other form is greenish-yellow in alkaline medium ($7.73 < \text{pH} < 13.0$) having $\lambda_{\text{max}} =$

410 nm. For I_2 , the color of one form is green in acidic medium ($1.0 < \text{pH} < 6.98$) having $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 365$ nm and the color of the other form is yellowish red in alkaline medium ($8.29 < \text{pH} < 13.0$) having $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 465$ nm. pK_{In} values are 6.73 and 7.78 at 35 °C for I_1 and I_2 respectively.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used for all the experiments. Solutions of sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid each 1 molar were made by dissolving in distilled water. Indicator I_1 (0.036×10^{-3} M) and indicator I_2 (0.249×10^{-3} M) solutions were obtained by dissolving requisite amounts in 2 : 1 alcohol and water mixtures. pK_{In} determination was carried out with published procedure⁵. The two concentrated solutions of NaOH and HCl, both of mol L⁻¹ were used. Solutions of different pH values were adjusted by addition of small volume of concentrated solutions by micropipette. The apparent pK_{In} values have been determined using Henderson-Hasselbach equation applicable for spectrometric titration.

A standard solution of indicator I_1 (0.036×10^{-3} M) and that of I_2 (0.249×10^{-3} M) along with exact (*N*/10) NaOH and (*N*/10) HCl solutions were prepared for evaluating molar extinction coefficient. Absorbances of seven differently concentrated solutions each of indicator I_1 and indicator I_2 were made by mixing varying amounts of indicator solutions along with different amounts of (*N*/10) NaOH and (*N*/10) HCl solutions keeping the total volume constant. The absorbances were recorded with the Systronics UV-visible spectrophotometer 118 at λ_{max} of both acidic and basic forms of the indicator I_1 and I_2 at 470 and 410 nm and at 365 and 465 nm respectively (Figs. 1a and 1b). Similarly molar extinction coefficient values of methyl orange were measured in acidic and basic forms.

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